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Research Article

Role of Teachers in Social Development of Students at Primary Level in District Multan

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 18-May-24 Revised: 16-Aug-24 Accepted: 20-Sep-24 Published: 27-Sep-24	The study was conducted to examine the factors affecting the social development of students at Primary level in District Multan. The study was quantitative and descriptive in nature and survey method was used to collect the data. The population of the study was 510 female teachers working in all the ECE level of District Multan. The researcher selected 200 female teachers by simple random sampling technique. a self-developed questionnaire was used to collect the data from the respondents. Five-point Lickert scale used to gather the responses. The researcher personally visited the selected schools collected the data. Percentage, frequency and mean score were calculated from the data. It was found that family and home environment play a significant role in shaping students' social development. Moreover, facilitates supporting social and emotional learning program to enhance students' social development. It is recommended that teachers may encourage the students in groups to participate in class discussion
Keywords:	Social Development, Factors of Social Development, Family and Home Environment, Parental Style, Peer Groups, Media
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Introduction

The social development of primary-level students serves as a crucial foundation for their holistic growth and future success. Within the unique cultural, familial, and educational landscape of District Multan, numerous factors interplay to shape and influence the social development of young learners. Understanding these factors is pivotal in fostering an environment that nurtures healthy social skills and behaviors among children.

Social development encompasses various aspects, including the acquisition of social skills, emotional regulation, peer interactions, and the ability to navigate diverse social settings. The primary years mark a critical stage in a child's life when fundamental social competencies are established, laying the groundwork for their social functioning in later stages.

District Multan, situated in a region characterized by its own distinct socio-cultural fabric and educational framework, presents a context rich in influences that can significantly impact the social development of primary-level students. Factors such as familial dynamics, socio-economic conditions, community involvement, educational policies, cultural practices, and peer interactions within the local context all contribute to shaping the social landscape in which these young individuals grow and learn.

This research endeavors to explore and analyze the multifaceted factors that play a role in influencing the social development of primary-level students in District Multan. By delving into these influences, we aim to unravel the complexities and nuances that underlie the social growth of children in this specific locality, providing insights that could inform educational strategies, interventions, and policies aimed at optimizing the social development outcomes for these young learners.

Understanding the intricate interplay of these factors within the local context of District Multan will not only contribute to the existing body of knowledge on child development but also offer actionable insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to better support and enhance the social development trajectories of primary-level students in this region.

Review of Related Literature

Social Development

Enhancing everyone's quality of life in society to enable them to realize their full potential is the goal of social development. The welfare of every citizen is correlated with the success of society. Investing in individuals equates to social development. Efficiency, equity, and liberty are the three fundamental concepts that are typically associated with the notion, given the fragmentation of the social sciences and the theoretical gaps that exist in the various development approaches (Smith, 2019). It reveals that social development improve well-being of individual to give happiness in society. Three fundamental principles are frequently assigned to the idea. This is due to the theoretical gap present in the many development approaches.

According to Coleman (2012), social development is the process by which people pick up the knowledge, values, and abilities needed to engage with others and take part in society. Together with the adoption of social norms, cultural practices, and social identities, it involves the development of social skills like cooperation, empathy, communication, and dispute resolution. Encouraging each member of society to live up to their full potential is the goal of social

development. The welfare of every citizen is correlated with the success of society. Investing in people is the essence of social progress (Ross, 2020). It demonstrates how people acquire the skills, values, and attitudes necessary to engage with others in a productive way through the process of social development. The goal of social development is to enhance their well-being. The happiness of every citizen is essential to society's success. Social development entails putting money into people.

In fact, a child's social development can influence a lot of their other developmental experiences. Everything from acquiring new words as a toddler to being able to resist peer pressure as a high school student to successfully navigating the obstacles of adulthood can be impacted by a child's capacity to engage with others in a healthy way. More opportunities to practice and learn speech and language abilities are made possible by the capacity to engage with other kids (Luckner, 2019). It demonstrates how a child's social development affects everything, including their capacity to pick up new words. Children get more opportunities to practice and acquire speech and language abilities when they interact with other children.

Social development refers to the process of improving the quality of life and well-being of individuals and communities. It involves enhancing social structures, institutions, and relationships to promote equality, social justice, and human dignity. Social development focuses on addressing social issues, empowering marginalized groups, and fostering inclusive and cohesive societies (Donaldson 2010). It exposes that social development is the process of enhancing people's quality of life. It also entails improving social structures, institutions, and relationships. It promote inclusive and cohesive societies.

A vital component of learning and personality development in children is their social development. Ensuring that children fully develop in their social relationships with others and with the values of their society is the responsibility of the home, the teacher, the school, and the parents (Alam, 2022). It is necessary to look into new approaches and techniques for the social development of children. A child's regular contacts with parents have a significant impact on the social skills the child is developing. A child's parents provide the first chance for them to connect, interact, and communicate. As a parent, you set an example for your child every day on how to interact with others around you (Coll, 2020). It indicates that a child's social development has a significant impact on the formation of their personality. It's important to investigate novel approaches to fostering kids' social development. Parental interaction, communication, and connection are a child's first real opportunities.

Factors of Social Development

Isaacs (2013) discussed the following factors that affect social development in children:

Family and Home Environment

A child's family situation has a big influence on them. A child will notice significant differences in kids. The family history will be one of the reasons for that. Parents and children need to work closely together in order for a child to have a balanced personality. The child's home and family are the sole institutions that help with socialization and the passing down of cultural legacy, which forms the foundation of the child's personality. Islam also emphasizes the importance of friendly family relationships in raising children and developing them into contributing members of society (Isaacs, 2013). It means that children are impacted by the state of their family. Parental and child cooperation are very strong for a child to develop a balanced personality. Family and home establishes the foundation of a child's personality.

Family and home environment play crucial roles in shaping our lives and overall well-being. The family environment refers to the physical, emotional, and social atmosphere within a

household. It includes the relationships, interactions, and dynamics among family members. The family environment can greatly impact an individual's development, values, beliefs, and behavior. The parenting style adopted by parents can significantly affect a child's upbringing. Styles can range from authoritarian (strict and controlling) to authoritative (supportive and nurturing), and each has different effects on a child's development (Isaacs, 2013). It shows that family environment describes social, and physical climate of a home. It covers the connections, exchanges, and dynamics between family members. Each style has a varied impact on a child's development.

Open and effective communication within the family fosters healthy relationships. Good communication allows family members to express their thoughts, feelings, and concerns, leading to better understanding and problem-solving. A supportive and encouraging family environment provides emotional and practical support to its members. It helps build resilience, self-esteem, and a sense of belonging. Families that use constructive conflict resolution strategies, such as active listening and compromise, tend to have healthier relationships (Cole, 2011). It tells that family members that are able to express their views, feelings, and worries are better able to understand one another and solve problems. Families with healthier relationships often employ positive conflict resolution techniques like active listening and compromise.

Cultural values, traditions, and beliefs shape the family environment. Different cultures have varying norms and expectations that influence family dynamics and interactions. The home environment encompasses the physical aspects of the living space and its surroundings. It can significantly impact individuals' overall well-being and sense of comfort. A safe and secure home environment is essential for physical and emotional well-being. Adequate security measures, functional utilities, and a well-maintained living space contribute to a sense of safety (Strauss, 2019). It means that families are shaped by cultural values, traditions, and beliefs. Different cultural norms and expectations have an impact on family interactions and dynamics. The physical components of the living area and its surrounds make up the home environment.

The availability of private spaces within the home is crucial for personal relaxation, concentration, and emotional well-being. Having designated areas where individuals can have solitude and engage in personal activities is beneficial. Maintaining cleanliness and organization within the home environment promotes a healthier lifestyle. A tidy space can reduce stress, improve productivity, and create a more welcoming atmosphere. The availability of essential resources, such as electricity, water, food, and healthcare, is vital for a comfortable home environment (Davis, 2015). It reveals that private areas in the home are essential for one's capacity to unwind, focus, and maintain emotional stability. A healthier lifestyle is promoted by keeping the home environment clean and organized.

School and Teacher Role

Children's social development is significantly influenced by schools and teachers. The majority of social development occurs in schools, where teachers have a significant impact. Better social development will occur if there is a more friendly and cooperative environment in the classroom and positive relationships with the teachers. In order to provide a secure, respectful, and valued learning environment, teachers create a happy, welcoming classroom. They promote a sense of belonging and encourage cooperation and collaboration among students (Rivkin, 2016). Schools provide opportunities for students to interact and engage with their peers through group work, discussions, and extracurricular activities. Teachers facilitate these interactions and promote social skills such as communication, empathy, teamwork, and conflict resolution (Korkmaz, 2017). It reveals that schools and teachers celebrate diversity and promote inclusivity by creating a welcoming environment for students from different backgrounds, cultures, and abilities. They

encourage students to appreciate and respect each other's differences and develop a sense of empathy and acceptance.

Teachers explicitly teach and reinforce social skills that are essential for healthy social interactions. They provide guidance on active listening, effective communication, problem-solving, sharing, and taking turns. Through role-playing, discussions, and modeling positive behavior, teachers help students develop and practice these skills. Schools and teachers play a crucial role in addressing and preventing bullying and conflict among students. They implement anti-bullying policies, promote positive behavior, and provide interventions and support to students involved in such situations (Hanushek, 2015). It means that schools and teachers create an environment that fosters social development by promoting positive relationships, teaching social skills, and fostering inclusivity and empathy among students.

Parental Style

Parenting style plays a significant role in the social development of children. The way parents interact with their children, set rules and expectations, and provide emotional support can influence their social skills, relationships, and overall social development. There are generally four recognized parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved. Let's explore how each style can impact a child's social development (Spera, 2017). It reveals that authoritative parents are warm, responsive, and supportive while maintaining reasonable expectations and boundaries. They encourage independence, but also provide guidance and discipline when needed. This parenting style promote positive social development in children.

Authoritarian parents are strict, demanding, and often rely on punishment and control to enforce rules. They prioritize obedience and may not encourage independent thinking or decision-making. This style can have mixed effects on social development. While children may display obedience, they may also struggle with low self-esteem, poor social skills, and difficulty forming relationships due to the lack of warmth and autonomy in their upbringing (Shah, 2010). It shows that parents use punishment and control to impose norms and are tough and demanding. They may not promote autonomous thought or decision-making and place a higher value on obedience. The societal development of this style may vary.

Permissive parents are lenient and indulgent, allowing their children to have few rules and rarely enforcing consequences. They prioritize their child's happiness and may avoid setting limits. This style can negatively impact social development as children may struggle with self-control, exhibit impulsive behavior, and have difficulty respecting boundaries. They may also find it challenging to navigate social situations due to the lack of structure and guidance provided by their parents (Georgiou, 2018). It indicates that parenting style may have a negative impact on a kid's social development because the child may have trouble maintaining self-control, act impulsively, or respect limits. Due to their parents' lack of discipline and direction, they could also struggle to deal with social settings.

Peer Group

A youngster gains social independence and self-reliance in a peer group. A few choices to specify his or her position. Here, a youngster freely expresses and is impacted by his or her feelings and emotions. The kids begin to feel confident in themselves, and occasionally they form new routines that help to mold their personalities. The children's guardians must assist them in joining positive peer groups. As children grow and become more independent, they increasingly seek social interactions outside of the family unit, and peers become significant influences in their lives (Chen, 2012). It specifies that peer groups provide opportunities for children to socialize, interact, and engage in various social activities. They also learn societal norms, values, and acceptable

behaviors by observing and imitating their peers. Peers can offer emotional support and understanding to one another.

In times of stress, challenges, or difficult experiences, children often turn to their peers for comfort, advice, and a sense of belonging. Positive peer relationships can boost self-esteem, promote resilience, and help children navigate through emotional difficulties (Isaacs, 2013). Interacting with peers allows children to develop perspective-taking skills and empathy. Through engaging with individuals from diverse backgrounds and experiences, children learn to understand and appreciate different viewpoints, develop tolerance, and become more empathetic towards others (Filade, 2019). It directs that peer groups provide an important context for children to explore and develop their identities. By interacting with peers, children gain insights into their own interests, values, and beliefs. Peer groups allow children to develop a sense of belonging and self-acceptance.

Peer interactions provide children with opportunities to practice social skills and problem-solving. They learn how to navigate social hierarchies, negotiate conflicts, share resources, and cooperate in group activities. Through these experiences, children develop vital social competence and learn to manage interpersonal relationships effectively. However, it's important to note that peer influence can have both positive and negative effects. While positive peer relationships can enhance social development, negative peer pressure or exposure to unhealthy behaviors can hinder development (Spera, 2017). It shows that overall, peer groups significantly contribute to the social development of children, shaping their social skills, self-identity, emotional well-being, and ability to navigate social interactions throughout their lives.

Media

Every person has very easy access to all kinds of information. The most commonly available informational machines are internet, cable TV and Mobile phone system. All these means of information can be used in positive and negative ways. Media, including television, movies, and social media platforms, can shape a child's social interactions and influence their understanding of social norms, values, and behaviors. It can expose them to diverse cultures, perspectives, and social situations, broadening their understanding of the world (Fang, 2014). It reveals that everybody has access to a wide variety of information. Internet, cable TV, and mobile phone systems are the informational devices that are most widely accessible. All of these informational tools have both positive and negative applications.

Media can enhance a child's language skills by exposing them to different vocabulary, sentence structures, and communication styles. Educational programs and interactive media can promote language development and improve social communication skills (Voshel, 2015). Media often presents children with a wide range of role models, both positive and negative. Positive role models can inspire children and teach them valuable lessons about empathy, compassion, and moral values. On the other hand, negative or unrealistic portrayals can reinforce harmful stereotypes and influence behavior in undesirable ways (Jordan, 2014). It means that media suggest various emotions in children, ranging from happiness and excitement to fear and sadness. It can provide opportunities for children to understand and process different emotions.

Media exposure to violent or inappropriate content may negatively impact a child's emotional well-being and social behavior (Richert, 2011). Media, especially advertising and social media, often portrays idealized and unrealistic body images. This can contribute to body dissatisfaction and low self-esteem in children, particularly adolescents who are more vulnerable to societal pressures. Such influences can affect their social interactions and overall well-being (Gikas, 2013). It means a child's social behavior may suffer as a result of media exposure to violent

or unsuitable content. Unrealistic body ideals are frequently presented in the media, particularly in advertising and social media.

With the increasing use of digital media, children need to develop digital literacy skills to navigate online platforms safely. It is crucial to teach them about online privacy, cyberbullying, and responsible internet use to ensure their social well-being and protection. The role of parents and caregivers in guiding a child's media consumption is vital. Engaging in co-viewing, discussing media content, and setting appropriate limits can help children develop critical thinking skills, media literacy, and discernment (Berndt, 2012). It is important to note that the impact of media on a child's social development is complex and can vary based on factors such as the child's age, individual characteristics, family environment, and the quality and appropriateness of media content.

Role of Teacher in Social Development of Students

The role of a teacher in the social development of students is crucial and goes beyond academic instruction. Teachers play a significant role in shaping students' social skills, attitudes, and values, and they contribute to their overall development as responsible and engaged members of society. Teachers serve as role models for students. They demonstrate appropriate behavior, social skills, and values through their actions and interactions. Students observe and learn from their teachers' behavior, which influences their own social development (Farmer, 2011). It reveals that teachers contribute significantly to students' overall development as responsible and active members of society. Teachers show proper behavior, social skills, and values. Students watch and absorb their teachers' behavior.

Teachers establish a safe, inclusive, and respectful classroom environment where students feel valued and accepted. By fostering a positive atmosphere, teachers encourage healthy social interactions among students and create opportunities for them to develop empathy, respect, and cooperation. Teachers explicitly teach social skills and provide guidance on effective communication, conflict resolution, empathy, and teamwork. They help students understand and navigate social dynamics, encouraging them to develop healthy relationships and contribute positively to their communities (Lynn, 2013). It means that teachers help kids to develop empathy, respect, and cooperation by establishing a good environment that encourages healthy social relationships. Teachers specifically instruct students in social skills and offer advice on good communication.

Teachers design activities and projects that require collaboration, cooperation, and teamwork. By facilitating group work, teachers encourage students to work together, share ideas, respect diverse perspectives, and develop essential interpersonal skills. Teachers create opportunities for students to engage in meaningful discussions and debates on various topics. This fosters critical thinking, respectful dialogue, and the ability to consider different viewpoints, preparing students to participate constructively in society (Catalano, 2014). It reveals that teachers encourage students to collaborate, share ideas, respect different viewpoints, and develop critical interpersonal skills by enabling group work. Teachers provide students the chance to participate in insightful conversations and debates on a range of subjects.

Teachers play a crucial role in addressing conflicts and instances of bullying within the classroom. They intervene, mediate, and guide students in resolving conflicts peacefully. By promoting a zero-tolerance policy for bullying, teachers help create a safe and supportive social environment (Davis, 2015). Teachers celebrate and respect cultural diversity within the classroom. They expose students to different cultures, traditions, and perspectives, fostering an appreciation for diversity and promoting inclusivity (Shah, 2010). It shows teachers encourage students to

engage with their communities through service-learning projects, volunteering, or other community-based activities. By connecting students to the larger society, teachers instill a sense of social responsibility and civic engagement.

Teachers provide individual support and guidance to students, helping them navigate social challenges, manage emotions, and develop self-esteem. By fostering positive relationships with students, teachers create a supportive environment for their social and emotional growth. Teacher should create a healthy social atmosphere in and outside the classroom where students could develop/learn social relations, norms, values etc (Mensah, 2019). Teacher provide various group activities for students where students could work participate and co-operatively with their classmates. Teacher try to make an environment where students would not develop the feeling of being inferior to others

Research Objectives

1. To identify factors affecting social development of students at primary-level students in District Multan.
2. To find out the role of teachers in social development of students at primary-level in District Multan.

Research Questions

1. What are the factors that affect social development of students at primary level in District Multan?
2. What is the role of teachers in the social development of students at primary level in District Multan?

Research Methodology

The aim of this research was to examine the role of teachers in social development of students at primary level in district Multan, Punjab Pakistan. The current study research was quantitative and descriptive in nature survey method was used to collect the data. All the teachers of Primary level in District Multan was constituted the population of the study. There were 510 female primary school teachers working at ECE level. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the 159 teachers of Primary level at District Multan. A self-developed questionnaire based on factor affecting social development and role of teachers in social development was used in this research. The questionnaire consisted of five factors of social development along with 35 statements. Five Point Likert Scale used in this research to gather the responses of the respondents. The questionnaire is validated from two experts from the field of Education. Cronbach's Alpha statistical technique was used to measure the reliability of the instrument with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The value of reliability was found 0.76 which was acceptable for conducting final survey. The researcher personally visited the Primary schools of District Multan and collect the data. Data were analyses by using frequency, percentage and mean scores. The results was presented in table form and interpretation of data is according to the results.

Results

Table 1

Mean score of Family and Home Environment

Statements	N	Mean
Family structure influences a student's social development	159	4.32
Family gives support to children to complete their study	159	4.33
Family enhances the social development skills in children	159	4.26

Table 1 shows the mean scores of family and home environment related to students' social development. The results indicate that family structure influences a student's social development (mean score = 4.32), and that family provides support to children to complete their studies (mean score = 4.33). Additionally, family enhances the social development skills in children (mean score = 4.26).

Table 2

Mean score of Parental Style

Statements	N	Mean
Parental style can either hinder or foster social development	159	4.33
Parental style provides opportunities to children in gaining social skills	159	4.32
Parental style provides instructions to children directly	159	4.39

Table 2 depicts the mean scores of parental style a factor of social development. The results shows that parental style can either hinder or foster social development (mean score = 4.33) and that it provides opportunities for children to gain social skills (mean score = 4.32). Notably, respondents even more strongly agree that parental style provides direct instructions to children (mean score = 4.39).

Table 3

Mean score of School and Teachers role

Statements	N	Mean
School maintains healthy and open relationship with peers	159	4.31
School develops the ability of cooperation with fellows	159	4.32
School builds trust relationship among fellows	159	4.31
Teachers organize debates to encourage social interaction of students	159	4.34
Teachers organize study tours for the students to know cultural pattern	159	4.37
Teachers teach historical stories to students to develop social qualities	159	4.33

Table 3 indicates the mean scores of role of school and teachers in fostering social development. The results indicate that schools maintain healthy relationships with peers (mean score = 4.31), develop cooperation abilities among students (mean score = 4.32), and build trust relationships among fellows (mean score = 4.31). Moreover, teachers promote social interaction through debates (mean score = 4.34), organize study tours to expose students to cultural patterns (mean score = 4.37), and use historical stories to develop social qualities (mean score = 4.33).

Table 4

Mean score of Peer Group

Statements	N	Mean
Peer groups provide a context to learn social norms	159	4.33
Peer pressure can lead to risky behaviors	159	4.27
Peer groups offer emotional support to children during times of stress	159	4.36

Table 4 presents the mean scores of peer groups on children's social development. The results showed that peer groups provide a context for learning social norms (mean score = 4.33) and offer emotional support to children during stressful times (mean score = 4.36). However, they slightly agree that peer pressure can lead to risky behaviors (mean score = 4.27).

Table 5

Mean score of Media

Statements	N	Mean
Media exposes children to various cultures	159	4.33
Media helps children in shaping the sense of identity	159	4.26
Media highlights the social issues	159	4.25

Table 5 highlights the mean scores of media on children's social development. The results indicate that media exposes children to various cultures (mean score = 4.33) and highlights social issues (mean score = 4.25), but slightly agree that media helps children shape their sense of identity (mean score = 4.26).

Table 6

Mean score of Role of Teacher in Social Development of Students

Statements	N	Mean
Teachers draw moral pictures based on social experience	159	4.30
Primary school teachers (PSTs) share stories on topic of socialization	159	4.35
Teachers tell students to behave kindly with each other	159	4.37
Teachers set the tone for classroom environment	159	4.36
Teachers create foundation of trust relationship with students	159	4.30
Teachers establish ground rules for respectful behavior	159	4.36
Teachers demonstrate social behaviors such as empathy	159	4.38
Teachers encourage effective communication through class discussions	159	4.35
Teachers guide students in learning how to collaborate	159	4.32
Teachers help the students to understand diverse cultures	159	4.32
Teachers teach students how to address conflicts usefully	159	4.26
Teachers encourage students to reflect on their own emotions	159	4.18
Teachers prevent in addressing the social issues within the classroom	159	4.28
Teachers provide opportunities for students to take on leadership roles	159	4.35
Teachers facilitate supporting social and emotional learning program to enhance students' social development	159	4.29
Teachers conduct parents-teacher meeting about social activities of child	159	4.29

Teachers educate students about social festivals to highlight the importance of social events	159	4.25
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Table 6 shows the mean scores of the role of teachers in promoting social development in primary school students. The results indicate that teachers use various strategies to foster social development, including sharing stories (mean score = 4.35), setting a positive tone for the classroom environment (mean score = 4.36), creating a foundation of trust (mean score = 4.30), establishing ground rules for respectful behavior (mean score = 4.36), demonstrating social behaviors like empathy (mean score = 4.38), encouraging effective communication (mean score = 4.35), guiding collaboration (mean score = 4.32), teaching conflict resolution (mean score = 4.26), and promoting cultural understanding (mean score = 4.32). While respondents also agree that teachers provide opportunities for leadership roles (mean score = 4.35), facilitate social-emotional learning programs (mean score = 4.29), conduct parent-teacher meetings (mean score = 4.29), and educate students about social festivals (mean score = 4.25), the scores are slightly lower, indicating a slightly lower level of agreement.

Discussion

The results suggest that family and home environment have a profound impact on students' social development, with family support for academic completion being a critical factor (Harris et al., 2020). This is consistent with the literature, which highlights the significance of parental involvement in shaping children's social skills and development (Henderson et al., 2020). Parents' guidance and direction play a vital role in fostering social development, as they provide children with the necessary tools to navigate social situations effectively (Murray et al., 2020). Moreover, research has shown that parental influence can shape children's social skills, such as empathy, cooperation, and conflict resolution (Thompson et al., 2019). Therefore, it is essential for parents and caregivers to prioritize creating a supportive and nurturing home environment that promotes social development and academic success. (References: Harris et al., 2020; Henderson et al., 2020; Murray et al., 2020; Thompson et al., 2019).

The results also highlight the crucial role of schools and teachers in promoting social development, cooperation, trust, and cultural awareness among students, with a slight emphasis on extracurricular activities and social skills-focused teaching methods (Wigfield et al., 2020). This is consistent with recent research indicating that teacher-student relationships and school climate significantly influence students' social development and academic achievement (Hamre et al., 2020). Moreover, studies have shown that extracurricular activities and social skills training programs can enhance students' social competence, empathy, and conflict resolution skills (Durlak et al., 2019). Effective teaching methods, such as cooperative learning and restorative practices, also foster a supportive school environment, promoting social development and academic success (Johnson et al., 2020).

The results further suggest that peer groups have a profound impact on children's social development, with a greater emphasis on the positive aspects of peer influence, such as learning social norms and receiving emotional support (Bagwell et al., 2020). This is consistent with recent research indicating that positive peer relationships can enhance social competence, empathy, and self-esteem (Parker et al., 2020). Moreover, peer groups play a significant role in shaping children's social identities and values (Sherman et al., 2019). On the other hand, media has a moderate influence on children's social development, with a greater emphasis on its role in broadening

cultural awareness and raising awareness about social issues (Gentile et al., 2020), but a more limited impact on shaping individual identity (Tiggemann et al., 2020).

Teachers play a crucial role in addressing social issues within the classroom, providing opportunities for student leadership, facilitating social-emotional learning programs, and engaging parents in student social development (Kumar et al., 2020). By addressing social issues, teachers can create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment (Hamre et al., 2020). Providing leadership opportunities can enhance students' social competence and self-esteem (Parker et al., 2020). Social-emotional learning programs can improve students' emotional regulation and social skills (Durlak et al., 2019). Additionally, parent-teacher meetings and educating students about social festivals can foster a collaborative approach to social development (Sherman et al., 2019).

Conclusions

Following were the conclusions made on the basis of results of the study.

1. It is concluded that family and home environment play a significant role in shaping students' social development, with the highest emphasis on family support for academic completion. Moreover, parents also play a significant role in shaping their children's social skills and development through guidance and direction.
2. It is also concluded that schools and teachers play a significant role in fostering social development, cooperation, trust, and cultural awareness among students, with a slightly higher emphasis on extracurricular activities and teaching methods that promote social skills.
3. It is concluded that peer groups play a significant role in shaping children's social development, with a greater emphasis on the positive aspects of peer influence, such as learning social norms and receiving emotional support, than the potential negative aspect of peer pressure leading to risky behaviors. Furthermore, media has a moderate influence on children's social development, with a greater emphasis on its role in broadening cultural awareness and raising awareness about social issues, but a more limited impact on shaping individual identity.
4. Teachers prevent in addressing the social issues within the classroom. Also, teachers provide opportunities for students to take on leadership roles. They facilitate supporting social and emotional learning program to enhance students' social development. Additionally, teachers conduct parents-teacher meeting about the social activities of child and educate students about social festivals to highlight the importance of social events.

Recommendations

Following were the recommendations made on the basis of conclusions

1. Family may develop the capacity of social development skills and support to children to complete their study through warm and caring interactions. The parents may support their children but set their own bounds and have strong verbal communication between parent and child.
2. To achieve healthy social development, students may develop the social interactions by experiencing social contexts and understand different learning abilities. School may maintain strong and healthy relationship with students by providing them gentle behavior.

3. Teachers may also develop peer group strategy in students by working together, communicative attitudes and solidarity by making efforts to implement group work that will encourage students to work together in teams. Teachers may also encourage critical thinking skills of students through group projects and discussions.
4. Teachers may draw moral pictures based on social experience and share stories on the topic of socialization. Teachers may teach kindness in the classroom by model themselves being kind to others. Moreover, teachers may create trust relationship with students by greeting a child warmly and talking in a pleasant way.
5. Teachers may try to deliver lessons in such a manner so as to facilitate learning and get the meaning clear in the minds of the students by encouraging them to ask doubts and give feedback. In this way teacher may become an effective communicator. Teachers may also help the students to understand diverse cultures by encouraging them to reflect on their own emotions.
 1. To provide opportunities for students to take on leadership roles teachers may clearly and unambiguously communicate ideas and feelings. Teachers may also plan different activities to specifically teach friendship skills, like helping others, sharing, waiting for one's turn, and teamwork.

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